

ANALYSIS OF TRAFFIC PROBLEMS OF ENSURING TRAFFIC SAFETY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN TASHKENT

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Annotation

This article analyzes the effectiveness of using Global Positioning System and other automatic warning systems in improving the existing traffic safety on highways. In addition, the role of this in ensuring safe driving was revealed by transmitting information about the most important road requirements for the driver while driving.

Key words: Car, road, driver, information, traffic, traffic safety, system, economy, method.

The use of cars is now a national economy covering almost all fields and their work high-quality and efficient organization is one of the most important and necessary tasks. All cars on the highway means of traffic regulation, road signs, road lines and public road acts in accordance with the rules and instructions. On the roads cars are driven by different people and each for himself chooses a convenient direction, order and management method. The driver's actions with certain dangerous effects for other participants on the road does not count.

The interaction of cars in traffic is the amount of movement the more it is, the more it increases.

Violation of the rules by car drivers, follow them Many roads due to traffic accidents traffic accidents occur. Committed by the driver Accidents happen mainly in dangerous situations and conflict points. Dangerous situations exist on roads with high traffic speed, The increase in the number of cars requires strong attention from the driver, safe it requires skill and quality knowledge on the order of movement Generally by means of a safe Organization of movement on the roads of the car the geometric measure of the maximum flow of vehicles take advantage of its different styles to ensure a safe movement routine and it is a system of activities aimed at ensuring high bandwidth. Q. H. Action in Azizov's textbook "fundamentals of the Organization of movement security" more about the rules and methods of many procedures on the organization of security data given.

The organization of movement security is increasingly present today it is ranked among the current issues. Internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Directorate General for traffic safety of the Ministry until November 2021 statistics on road-traffic accidents that occur on Republican roads published information.

According to him, over the past 10 months of the year, a total of 7,681 Yth listed. They had 1,964 lives, 6,886 to varying degrees the body was injured. It has also shed light on the reasons for the origin of this Yth. 1782 YTH Yth due to improper Organization of road movement or failures in roads listed. This represents 23.2 percent of total road traffic accidents. In 1,705 cases, the infantry had no place to fire. by crossing the road from an unspecified location (22.2 percent) link. 1,221 Ythspeed exceeding the norm sending has occurred due to. In the data, it can be seen that in 7.6% of incidents, i.e. 584, pedestrians are hit in the pedestrian space sent. The driver driving the car over a long period of time gets tired of the effects of noise vibrations and toxic gases emanating from the engine and loses control efficiency, a certain amount of attention. One of the main reasons for this is the operation of the engine with noise and vibration. Because nowadays, almost all cars moving in the streets are driven by oil fuels and the types of fuels that are an alternative to them . Naturally in this case, the noise and vibrations in the engine will be higher. To prevent such situations, the percentage of electric vehicles in moving traffic should be increased, and full electric vehicles will be required in the future.

Today, with the increase in the number of electric cars, modern technologies are becoming widely popular, providing information to the driver about the traffic situation in the control process, general information about the road (turns, chimneys, traffic lights and pedestrian spaces). In particular, global space navigation systems (GPS – Global Positioning System, (GLONASS – Globalnaya Navigatsionnaya Sputnikovaya Sistema) used in modern cars are systems that allow you to determine the geographical position, direction and speed of movement of objects moving at their desired point, at any time of the day. Apart from these, the exact time can be determined by this system in 1 nanosecond (0.00000001 SEC) accuracy. The system was commissioned by the United States Department of defense in the 70s of the 20th century the unit had been developed for military purposes, but in 1983 in other areas were also allowed to be used. In 1991, GPS technologies were introduced by the former USSR allowed to be bought by their Republics. System in the middle of the 90s fully launched. The main element of the GPS navigation system are 24 sun ways, they are 6 ta to different orbits, 60° relative to each other placed in the corner. Each the satellite has a 12-hour orbit around the globe. Each sister's weight is 800 kg.ni, 5 m long.dan makes up more (sun counting their batteries). Scientific research satellite on the organization of Motion safety found that navigation technology has a positive effect on Traffic Safety.

Availability and accuracy of the Global Positioning System transportation using highways, streets and mass transit systems it serves to provide high efficiency and safety for its tools. This the system is widely used all over the world today, it is used by cars all movement during the movement of the car, giving information about the location provides information on directions. This location technology, geographic systems that can display data can display data on display screens or automatic transfer to computers, shipping and forwarding it is used very efficiently in transportation.

The use of a this system in vehicles is the driver's improves movement in unknown places, increases alertness and stress levels reduces. An international study has shown that using a GPS device reduces the number of miles traveled by 16 percent, and travel in an unknown area it cuts its time by 18 percent. In addition service stations, maintenance and accident Services Location, traffic levels of road sections, etc provides information about. The system Car roads Primary School Buildings, Safety permanent on the location of the cameras and other dangerous road sections drivers are alerted through an updated database. Thus in advance the possibility of violation of traffic rules for co-drivers warning and conflicting points causing traffic accidents provides information about. The this system warns drivers of radar cameras that control high speed of movement from various dangers, crashes helps to save. Instead of a conclusion, it can be said that the movement that exists on the roads of the car this systems and other automatic alarms in increasing security the application of systems is highly efficient. This system the most important requirements of the order of movement for drivers driving a car, information about the rules of measurement and the general path status in large volumes transmits and warns of danger.

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